

The Potentials of Hague Convention on Inter-Country Adoption for Child Adoption Practices in Nigeria

Hope Damilola Williams-Akintan

Department of Politics and International Relations
Faculty of Management and Social Sciences
Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria
williamsdamilola21@gmail.com;+234813 5884507

&

Olubunmi Damilola Akande

Department of Politics and International Relations
Faculty of Management and Social Sciences
Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria
akande.olubunmi@lcu.edu.ng;+234 808 203 6647

Abstract

The Hague Convention on Inter-country Adoption is founded on the concepts that necessitate a far more audacious attempt to regulate and manage inter-country adoption on a worldwide scale. This study is centered on the significance of the 1993 Hague Convention on inter-country adoption. This convention places priority on child's best interest during adoption processes. The focus on the child's interest is achieved by taking into account the principle's international, regional, and national legal provisions, as well as their interpretation and application in child adoption practices. In the long run, the convention will contribute in the development of new initiatives to promote bilateral and multilateral adoption relations. The objectives of this study are to accentuate the importance of the Hague Convention on the Adoption of Children in Nigeria and to explore the issues as regard to Child Adoption in Nigeria. This study found that, while inter-country adoption is legal in Nigeria, implementing Hague Convention on Inter-country Adoption will be beneficial in preventing child abduction, sale, or trafficking. One of the study's recommendations is the Hague Convention will be beneficial to the Nigerian government as evaluation would show areas where the Hague Convention's implementation process is deficient, allowing the government to offer alternative methods to streamline the process. This would also benefit adoption agencies by increasing the effectiveness and significance of the educational and infrastructure services provided to people seeking adoption.

Keywords: Hague Convention, Children, Child Adoption, Orphanage, Inter-country Adoption

Introduction

The legal relationship between the child and the biological parents is ended when a child is adopted, and a new one is created between the child and the adoptive parent. There is no other mechanism under English law for parents to renounce parental responsibility for their minor child that lasts until maturity other than this specific child-related order (Lowe & Douglas, 1998). The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989) and the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child (1990), both fundamental international and African regional legal instruments on children's rights, agree that the family is the best environment for a child to grow up in. Nigeria, the study's location, ratified and domesticated these two instruments through the Law of the Child Act of 2003.

Adoption can be defined as the legal transfer of all parental rights that a biological parent has to a child, as well as the assumption by the adopting parents of all parental rights of the biological parents that are being terminated and are assumed in their entirety by the adoptive parents, including responsibility for the child's care and supervision, nurturing and training, physical, emotional, and financial well-being (Christopher et al, 2018). Adoption is a form of alternative care for children who are unable to remain in their family environment under the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child of 1989. It serves as a means of preventing child abuse, including child trafficking, and allows adopted children to access good education and prevent them from being placed in institutions. Child adoption is a highly publicized issue in Nigeria, and is viewed as a permanent and life-changing decision that affects both the baby and the adopting family or household (Palacios, Adroher, Brodzinsky, Grotevant, Johnson, Juffer, Martínez-Mora, Muhamedrahimov, Selwyn, Simmonds & Tarren Sweeney, 2019).

Adoption is a permanent change in status and requires societal recognition (Krause and Meyer, 2007). There is no legal distinction between a biological child and an adopted child, though some jurisdictions may have exceptions. Criticism of modern-day slavery, exploitation, and the sale and trafficking of babies has provided insight into adoption practices, as well as tales of exploitation, anger, sadness, depression, and guilt experienced by vulnerable young women and adoptive parents (Bartholet, 2007). Nigeria has pledged to protect the rights and welfare of the Nigerian child by signing international conventions such as the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child (ACRWC) and the UNCRC, and the Nigeria Child Right Act (CRA) (Ojewole & Nwozichi, 2014). This obvious fact is demonstrated by initiating actions to ensure its observation and popularization. Section 125(1) of the Child Rights Act for example, provides, among other things, that the State, as well as the Federal Government, establish and maintains a service designed to meet the needs of a child who has been or may be adopted within each State and the Federal Capital Territory (Olayinka and Aderinto, 2019).

The Inter-country Adoption Universal Accreditation Act of 2012 requires that an accredited or approved adoption service provider act as the primary provider in every

Convention or non-Convention inter-country adoption case, and that adoption service providers providing any adoption services be accredited or approved, or supervised or exempted. Some learned writers argue that adoption is practiced in Nigeria under native law and custom, but a careful examination reveals that what they described as adoption is guardianship, fostering, or some other peculiar indigenous concepts. (UNODC Nigeria, 2021). This brings to fore one of the complexities surrounding adoption practices in Nigeria.

Statement of Problem

The Hague Convention on Protection of Children and Co-operation in Respect of Inter-Country Adoption (Convention), which offers the safeguards and framework for international cooperation on inter-country adoption, aims to ensure that inter-country adoptions are carried out in an ethical and transparent manner. However, many African countries' illegal adoption processes have been questioned for their use of children in illegal activities and trade around the world (Preston, 2021). African countries that have received international adoption attention include Nigeria, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, South Africa, Mali, Ghana, the Ivory Coast, Morocco, Uganda, and Burkina Faso. In Nigeria, cases of child abuse such as the use of underage children for street hawking, alms begging and domestic help remain a challenge despite the adoption and domestication of the Child Right Law. Nigeria's non-involvement with well regulated inter-country child adoption procedures signalled through their lack of endorsement of a recognised adoption convention like the 1993 Hague convention on the Protection of Children and Cooperation in Respect of Inter-country Adoption (HCCH) deepens the shortcomings highlighted above.

In line with this, this study aims to project the importance of the Hague Convention on the Adoption of Children in Nigeria and to explore some of the concepts and issues that affect Child Adoption in Nigeria.

Methodology

This main research approach employed in this study is the qualitative method. This study adopted a descriptive analysis which included primary and secondary data. Primary data was acquired through semi-structured interview with personnel from the Ministry of Youths and Social Development, as well as representatives from various orphanages and adoption agencies involved in inter-country adoption in Lagos State whilst secondary data was obtained from libraries, books, blogs, journals, magazines, newspapers, and other relevant materials related to the research.

The Concept of Child Adoption

Adoption is the formal establishment of a parent-child relationship, complete with all of its obligations and rights, between a child and an adult who is not the child's biological parent. It is

an all-encompassing idea that grants legal rights for the adopter and adoptee to unite as a family. Child adoption was recognized as an alternative method of caring for children who are temporarily or permanently removed from their home environment by the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989), including children who are unable to stay in their family setting (Ojelabi, Osamor & Owumi, 2015). The legal right for the adopter and adoptee to unite as a family is provided by child adoption, which is a worldwide idea.

Adoption is a social construct that aims to address the needs of two distressed groups of people. When biological parents are unwilling or incapable of raising a child within the family as a result of unwanted pregnancy or due to financial issues in the family, they may experience distress and might opt for abortion as a means to evade the embarrassment and societal disapproval associated with being pregnant outside of marriage. This could put the child's life in danger (Aniebue P & Aniebue U, 2008). The society views this as a genuine method of rounding up children who are considered "unwanted" in the society and placing them in families where they are highly desired, to avoid the shame associated with infertility and childlessness (Stibbe, 2005).

The concept of adoption exists across cultures and countries and may be traced all the way to ancient Rome under 6th century AD Roman Law, Codex Justinianus, when the family patriarch was poised to die without a male heir, an heir could be provided from another family adoption (Jones, 2019). Historically, adoption is a transaction between an adopter and a slave, where the adopter liberates the slave from the bondage of slavery (Butlinski et al, 2019). It is legally a family relationship that obligates both adopters and adoptees to give the adopted child the same permanent care, last name, rights, and privileges as a biological child, including inheritance rights (Tajudeen, 2013). Different views of child adoption exist in Nigeria as a result of the variety of legal systems that regulate daily life. Adoption practices under customary and religious laws (informal/traditional law, familial adoption) are very different from adoption under state law (formal/statutory adoption). Since Nigeria's official adoption law is a British creation, it reflects the social structure of the modern West (Zermatten, 2010).

Cultural Conceptions of Child Adoption

Indigenous African Conception of Child Adoption

African traditional law systems have incorporated provisions for various kinds of adoption of children ever since antiquity (ACPF, 2012). African customary laws differ from Western concepts of adoption, which include severance and replacement of familial relationships. In accordance with African customary law, only a limited number of rights and obligations over a

child may be transferred (Rwezaura & Wanitzek, 1991). Since customary law is a living document, it varies from one ethnic group to another and evolves through time.

The concept of child adoption varies among Nigerians. Just to confirm its popularity in Ebonyi State, a survey showed 80% of respondents was aware of child adoption in the South East (Agbo, 2014). Kinship adoption is the mutually agreed-upon placement of children in the homes of relatives without the involvement of agencies. The child may be adopted by grandparents, uncles, aunts, or even another close relative. The child will reunite with the same family and use their biological parents' names. The child will also acquire property and other rights due to his paternity. Kinship adoption has declined in popularity, while formal child adoption has grown in popularity (Hegar & Scannapieco, 2017). Many people believe that adopting a child without first fulfilling the procedures for adoption or adoption itself is wrong. This view is consistent with the method of obtaining children through a baby factory, where money is simply exchanged, enabling a woman to become a mother in an instant (Omeire et al 2015). The approach of producing babies at factories so that people may exchange for a price without consideration for the safety and wellbeing of the adoptee is not in line with Nigerian legal requirement for adoption.

Prior to the colonial era, child adoption was not a part of Igbo culture in Igbo territory (Nwaoga, 2013). The Igbo people are proud of and highly value their culture. Nowadays, most modern cultures have found their way into various regions, including Igbo land, as a result of civilization and its impact on society. In Igbo culture, the adoptive family bestows the privileges, rights, and obligations of a child and heir on the adopted child. Child adoption has returned to Igbo Land due to the nature of Igbo culture, despite the fact that many people were opposed to its introduction. In Igbo land, omenani, or family custom, is the mechanism by which the social ethos is assessed, social values are passed down through generations, and young children are socialised to aid in their education (Arinze, 2008).

It is interesting to note that people in the Yoruba region of the south-west of Nigeria appear to be more open to adopting children. Adoption is strongly supported by the Yoruba cultural principle that "oriomo lo npeomowa'ye" (meaning "a child generally invites yet to be born children to come to the physical realm") (Tajudeen, 2013). Adoptive parents find it easier to accept adopted children into their families and communities, which help them, win the blessings of biological children. However, Yoruba cultural beliefs view adopted children as outcasts who are more likely to engage in antisocial behaviour (Ojelabi, Osamor & Owumi, 2015). As a result, couples considering adoption are discouraged by the prospect of tarnishing their family's reputation if the adopted child turns out to be anti-social. Instead, men in infertile marriages are pushed to marry other women.

Islamic Concept of Child Adoption

The Qur'anic decree forbids adoption. As a result, adoption is not accepted in regions where the Islamic Personal Law is in effect. Guardianship is a recognized topic under Islamic law. A

number of verses in the Holy Qur'an contain references to the religious authorities that discuss guardianship under Islamic law. Under the right conditions, any Muslim who is responsible, sane, and an adult may serve as a guardian. (AbdulHameed, 2013)

Adoption is not recognized as foster care, guardianship, or kinship adoption due to the need for the adoptee to return to their birth family and stake a claim to inheritance. Islam has created a concept known as kafala, which allows a child who is incapable of being cared for by their biological parents to be taken in by another family permanently, but the child is not allowed to take the family name or inherit from the family (O'Halloran 2015). Kafala is the voluntary promise to support a child's care, maintenance, education, and protection in the same manner that a birth parent would, but without inheritance or included in the family will. Similar to foster care, this is a social welfare system for the upbringing of children. Kafala, in this context, refers to a form of child custody and guardianship, often used in Islamic cultures, which is similar to adoption but retains some differences, particularly regarding family ties, identity, and inheritance rights (Shabnam, 2008).

Theoretical Framework

In this work, the Family System theory will be deployed to analyze the different processes surrounding child adoption.

Family Systems Theory

Family Systems Theory is a scientific theory of human behaviour that defines the family unit as a complex social system, in which members interact to influence each other's behaviour (Science Direct, 2022). For this research, this idea is heavily structured around at least two key elements. The first is that a family is a system to which systems theory research and observation apply. The second is that emotion is a fundamental or dominant force in human development within the family system. When these two fundamental principles are combined, the family system is described as an emotional unit in which each family member influences each other (Pollard & Boyd).

The family system theory outlines a series of organic interactions that strengthen cohesion and stability both inside and across families. Good deeds in daily life can boost the development of flourishing children; provide protection against stress and instability (Families and schools together, 2022). Family Systems Theory considers the family to be a living system, with each level of the hierarchy, including a cell, organ, organism (person), group (family), organization (neighborhood), community (city), society (country), and supranational system. It begins with an understanding of the significant impact of emotions in family dynamics.

Family Systems Theory considers each family member to be a member of the living system hierarchy, making family system concepts accessible to social interactions beyond the

family. It is believed to be able to address the issues that lead to divorces, which have a negative effect on children and young people. Early studies have shown that the mother-child bond has a significant impact on a child's development and the relationship between the child and all other family members has the greatest influence on their function and growth (Montelli &Hurst, 2022).

Family therapists must understand the beginning and source of the problem in order to aid either the family or the child who has been primarily affected by the outcome. This theory is appropriate to analyze all the cumulative systems that interact and relate, although diverging, in order to pinpoint the specific responses of each member of the adoption triad which are the child, Birth parents and the Adoptive parents. Each system has standards, duties, and regulations that influence psychological growth, and to fulfill a conventional process, all component, connected to the child are highly important (Omeire, 2016). Family systems theory provides a framework for understanding the complexities of the child adoption process. It highlights the importance of examining family dynamics, communication, boundaries, and adaptation when a new member is added through adoption. By applying the principles of family systems theory, families can navigate the adoption process more effectively and provide a supportive and nurturing environment for the adopted child.

Child Adoption Process in Nigeria

Agbonika & Agbonika (2021) provide insights into the child adoption process in Nigeria. It involves the following steps:

- 1. Selection of an adoption service provider:** The first step in adopting a child in Nigeria is to decide whether or not to use a licensed adoption service provider that can help with the adoption. Adoption service providers must be licensed by the state in which they operate, and the Ministry of Youths and Social Development provides information on selecting an adoption service provider on its relevant website.
- 2. Application for consideration on eligibility:** To adopt a child from Nigeria, meeting both Nigerian government and destination country's immigration requirements is crucial. The concerned person needs to apply for eligibility through the Social Welfare Office of the child's Nigerian state. If the child is being taken to the United States, an additional step involves filing an orphan petition with the U.S. Department of Homeland Security. Meeting age requirements and demonstrating factors, like livelihood and residence, is also necessary.
- 3. Be matched with a child:** When eligible to adopt and if a child is ready for adoption, Nigeria's central adoption authority offers a referral. Families must assess if they can provide for a child's needs and a lasting home. The child must meet Nigeria's adoption criteria and also qualify as an orphan under U.S. Immigration Law if being taken to the U.S.

- 4. Adopting or Gaining Legal Custody of a Child in Nigeria:** The process for finalizing the adoption (or gaining legal custody) in Nigeria generally includes the Role of Adoption authority, the Role of the court, documents required for adoption and registration.

Emergent Issues Relating to Child Adoption in Nigeria

Unexpectedly, the culture of child adoption is currently spreading across the nation. Adoption was not really a tradition that was widely practiced in the nation up until recently. However, as more Nigerians incline toward the practice, the pattern now appears to be changing. Nevertheless, these changes have negative implication on child trafficking, sales of babies and exploitation of young girls.

Child Trafficking

West and Central Africa has long been a hub for child trafficking, which involves recruitment, transportation, transfer, harbouring, or reception of a child for forced labour, slavery, or sexual exploitation. There have been reports of organ harvesting, sexual exploitation, forced marriages, and the trafficking of children for adoption. The majority of children who have been trafficked have been between the ages of 8 and 12 when they can work as domestic workers or farm labourers (Godwin, *The Guardian*, 2020).

These victims are tricked into becoming pregnant for financial gain, taken hostage and kept against their will, and mistreated and assaulted while working in baby factories. Even the children themselves are transported under covert circumstances to various places (Makinde, 2016).

Baby Factories

Baby factory is a word generically used to classify a location where women and young girls are encouraged or forced to get pregnant for selling their babies (Eseadi, Achagh, Ikechukwu-Ilomuanya & Ogbuabor, 2015). The operations of illegal baby factories appear to be on the rise in Nigeria. Often times, these come in form of small businesses disguised as private medical clinics, orphanages, or even social welfare homes. Although described as the third most common crime in the country after drug trafficking and financial fraud by a 2006 UNESCO report, efforts to stop its operation have found little success (Atiomo, 2021).

In over a decade, several locations have been uncovered by security agencies across the country with many pregnant women and young girls (Ezeah & Achonwa, 2015). This challenge is becoming alarming, threatening, and pejorative to the safety of young girls and women who in most cases are coerced to participate in this act, as well as the babies that are products of these processes. The prevalence of human trafficking, abuse, and sexual violence within Africa cannot be divorced from the growing practice of baby factories in Nigeria. Notwithstanding, this is not

to establish a definite causation between baby factories, human trafficking, abuse, and sexual violence but a justification that the climate these prevalent abuses create provide a fertile ground for baby factories to thrive in Nigeria (Eseadi et al. 2015).

Allusion has been made to a link between human trafficking, sexual violence and the baby factory practice in Nigeria with the central assumption that prevalent abuses provide conducive conditions for the establishment of baby factories. On the other side, reception towards the idea of baby factory has been enhanced by the socio-cultural factors demonizing childlessness and stigmatizing adoption, surrogacy or other form of assisted reproductive techniques (Omeire et al, 2015; Makinde, 2016). This prevalent social perception of ideal fertility criteria has forced so many childless couple into seeking solace and solution in deviating and unscrupulous ways within society. The Nigerian society is driven by a traditional belief that values and prioritizes fertility especially reproduction within marriages and the entire family system (Ezeah & Achonwa, 2015). Although there are similarities in the processes of baby commodification between Nigeria and other parts of the globe, the phenomenon of baby factory in Nigeria has degenerated to a serious dehumanizing process where some young girls and women are held hostage and turned into baby manufacturing engines. This is not a question of altruism as the case may be in some surrogacy arrangement but rather an intentional act by some unscrupulous actors within the country to profit from the exploitation and dehumanization of babies, young girls, and women (Godwin, *The Guardian*, 2020).

Loose Adoption Practices on Child Adoption

Loose adoption practice is not widely recognized term in the context of child adoption. However, informal or traditional adoption practices in Nigeria can sometimes be less regulated compared to formal legal child adoption processes. These informal practices are often referred to as "customary adoption" or "traditional adoption." Nigeria is a culturally diverse country with numerous ethnic groups, each having their own customs and traditions, including those related to adoption. In some communities, traditional or customary adoption practices have been in existence for generations. These practices involve the transfer of a child's care and upbringing from the biological family to another family or individual within the community. Customary adoptions might be done due to reasons like infertility, the desire for additional children, or as a way to strengthen family ties. Unlike formal legal adoptions, customary adoptions may not always follow standardized legal procedures. This can lead to challenges in terms of legal recognition, inheritance rights, and protection for the adopted child (Onayemi & Aderinto, 2017). Customary adoptions are often based on verbal agreements, community consensus, or traditional rituals. Documentation might be minimal, if at all, leading to potential difficulties in establishing legal parent-child relationships.

The coexistence of both formal and informal adoption processes in Nigeria, particularly when it comes to relying on kinship ties as a condition for adoption can indeed create complexities and challenges in the adoption landscape. This complicates adoption process as individual easily transfer from informal adoption to formal adoption without going through the required legal processes. This kind of arrangement creates obstacles at the inter-country adoption level. Informal adoption practices are solely based on kinship ties are deeply rooted in cultural norms and traditions. Nowadays, many Nigerian communities prioritize maintaining close family connections and networks. As a result, it's common for children to be adopted by relatives or close family friends when their biological parents are unable to care for them due to various reasons such as death, illness, poverty, or other personal circumstances. Decisions about adoption are made collectively within the community, and there might not be stringent legal procedures involved. This can allow for quicker responses to the needs of the child and provide a support system that draws on the strength of extended families. However, the informality of these arrangements can create challenges when individuals wish to transition from informal to formal adoption. While informal adoption might provide immediate support for the child, it might lack the legal framework necessary for long-term stability, inheritance rights, and other legal protections. This transition can be especially complex due to the lack of clear documentation or legal procedures to establish the transfer of parental rights (Nwachukwu, Nwachukwu, Adebayo, Cadmus & Owoaje, 2020).

Interactions from the ministry officials revealed that when it comes to international adoption, the complexities of transitioning from informal to formal adoption can pose challenges. Many receiving countries require a clear legal process and documentation to recognize the adoptive relationship and ensure that the child's rights are protected. The lack of such documentation and legal oversight from informal adoption can hinder the acceptance of the adoption by foreign countries. Inter-country adoption involves adhering to both the laws of the sending country (Nigeria) and the receiving country. The lack of standardized formal adoption procedures in Nigeria, especially for cases transitioning from informal to formal adoption, can result in difficulties in meeting the legal requirements of both countries. This can create delays, uncertainties, and potential obstacles in the inter-country adoption process.

Social Prejudices on Adoption in Nigeria

The stigma attached to adoption is a major issue in Nigeria, with many Nigerians assuming it is the offspring of drug addicts, criminals, mentally handicapped people, prostitutes, and the likes. Another social problem is the maltreatment of adopted children by their adopters, who often take advantage of them through physical abuse, sexual assault, or child labour (Makinde, 2016). Worse yet, these adopted children may have faced neglect or abuse simply because the

adoptive couples may have eventually regained their fertility and had their biological children. In addition, several cultural groups in Nigeria construct social classes based on the sociocultural preference for having children.

The most important details is that only legitimate and biological sons of the family have access to the supreme authority that enables entitlement to resources, and that the chiefs of the extended family make the majority of the decisions about inheritance and the disposal of the father's assets after his passing. This can lead to a child being estranged from and ignored by the extended family, which can be harmful to the child's healthy social and psychological development (Iloka, 2021). Furthermore, adopted children may be exposed to neglect or abuse when adoptive couples eventually birth biological children. The distribution of family wealth could also be problematic as popular traditional conceptions on inheritance practices endorse biological offspring as legitimate beneficiaries of family wealth. In many cases, members of extended family take majority of decisions on inheritance and distribution of assets when parents pass on. This can lead to a child being estranged from and ignored by the extended family, which can be harmful to the child's healthy social and psychological development (Iloka, 2021).

Hague Convention

The Hague Conference on Private International Law (Hague Conference) produced the Hague Convention on Protection of Children and Co-operation in Respect of Inter-country Adoption commonly known as the Hague Adoption Convention, was adopted on May 29, 1993. It entered into force on May 1, 1995. This convention was established to address specific issues with international adoption, such as legally binding standards, supervision, and communication and cooperation between authorities involved in any particular adoption with a focus on safeguarding the best interests of the children involved and promoting cooperation among countries participating in such adoptions (Sargent, 2004).

The Hague Convention was the first significant step towards establishing global minimum standards for cross-border adoption practices. It addressed the need for legal procedures to thwart threats such as document fraud, kidnapping and child trafficking, and unregulated companies controlling the adoption process. States are obligated to ratify it and incorporate it into both domestic and international law. The agreement acknowledged the need for a minimal set of international norms governing international adoptions that each participating state could review, accept, and comply by while being sure that other Hague members were doing the same (Bartholet, 1993). Article 1 of the 29 May 1993 convention on the protection of children and international adoption cooperation states that “a child who cannot find a suitable family in their state of origin may benefit from an international adoption by receiving

the benefit of a permanent family.” International adoptions must be made in the child's best interests and with respect for their fundamental rights to prevent child abduction, sale, and trafficking.

The main objectives of the Convention are set out in Article 1:

- i. To establish safeguards to ensure that inter-country adoptions only take place after the best interest of the child have been properly assessed and in circumstances which protect his or her fundamental rights.
- ii. To establish a system of co-operation amongst Contracting States to ensure that those safeguards are respected and thereby prevent the abduction, the sale of, or traffic in children.
- iii. To secure the recognition in contracting states of adoptions made in accordance with the convention.

These objectives have accompanying guidelines that aid adherence to the Hague requirements and standards for adoption processes.

Lammerant and Hofstetter, (2008) captures some of the requirements signatories to the Hague Convention which are expected to be adhered to. They include:

- 1 Parties to the convention are required to create a "Central Authority" in their nation, typically an organization, to oversee the process. The Department of State, for instance, serves as the central authority in the United States.
- 2 If the child has been found a home in his or her birth country despite being eligible for adoption by that country, inter-country adoptions may move forward.
- 3 An accrediting body, which approves agencies on behalf of the Department of State, is required to review agencies that have filed Hague complaints.
- 4 Adoption fees must be itemized and disclosed by accredited agencies.
- 5 A Hague Adoption Certificate or a Hague Custody Declaration must be given to each adopted child.
- 6 The correct forms and visa categories must be filled out by prospective adoptive parents.

Discussion, Conclusion and Recommendations

The major significance of being a member of the Hague convention is safeguarding and protecting the children from exploitation which include child abuse, emotional abuse and physical abuse and child trafficking. This Convention was established to protect children involved in cross border children's issues such as child trafficking, exploitation of young children especially the girls, Baby Factories etc. However, Nigeria is not a Signatory to the

Hague Convention on Inter-Country Adoption which has contributed to the decrease in the number of international adoptions from Nigeria alongside other issues such as insecurity and safety of children living in Nigeria. It is imperative for the Nigerian government to adopt a new perspective on the pressing issues to private international law in which the Hague Convention is on the top list. While Nigeria continues to address important concerns relating to women's and children's rights, such as through the National Agency for the Prohibition of Trafficking in Persons, enacting the Hague convention is now urgently required and long overdue. Similarly, there are compelling arguments in favour of the 2007 Maintenance Convention's enforcement of child support orders for Nigerian children by their absent parents who lives abroad or vice versa, as well as the 1980 Child Abduction Convention's amelioration of the negative effects of parental child abduction.

In recent years, the Nigerian government has been working to strengthen adoption laws and regulations to provide better protection for adopted children and ensure that their rights are upheld. Legal adoption processes are becoming more formalized and regulated. Furthermore, formal legal adoption processes are available in Nigeria, and these involve court-approved procedures to ensure the rights of the child and the adopting parents are protected. These formal adoptions provide legal recognition of the parent-child relationship and offer safeguards for the well-being of the child (Adonteng-Kissi, 2020). It is possible to make improvements to the Mechanism for Protecting the Interest of Nigerian Children Caught in Border Disputes. The Hague Conference has openly pushed for the adoption of these conventions in Africa for some time (Onyoja, 2022).

In accordance with the Hague Convention on Inter-Country Adoption and the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, this Act upholds the fundamental idea that the child's best interests come first (UNCRC) (O'Halloran, 2021). Children will be safeguarded internationally through this legal system (children who are victims of sale, trafficking or abduction, children who have endured improper placements abroad). Nigeria will also have an advantage in the international arena when other Hague Countries have no doubts about the children coming in from Nigeria because Nigeria is a signatory to the Hague Convention on Inter-Country Adoption (Onyoja, 2022). To address the challenges on the sale and trafficking of children, efforts have been made in Nigeria to improve adoption laws and regulations. These reforms aim to provide clearer guidelines for formal adoptions, ensuring proper legal documentation, transparency, and protection for the rights of adopted children. Standardizing adoption procedures can help streamline the transition from informal to formal adoption, making it more straightforward for individuals to pursue inter-country adoption if desired. In other words, the coexistence of formal and informal adoption practices in Nigeria, particularly those rooted in kinship ties, creates a complex landscape for adoption. While informal adoption offers flexibility and community support, the lack of legal recognition and documentation can complicate the transition to formal

adoption, especially in the context of international adoption. Efforts to strengthen adoption laws and provide clearer legal pathways can help address these challenges and ensure the well-being and rights of adopted children (Cox & Lieberthal, 2005).

The Hague Convention is a series of international treaties that aim to simplify and streamline processes involving international legal issues, such as child abduction, international adoption, service of process, and more. If Nigeria becomes a signatory to the Hague Convention, it can have several positive impacts on the country's reputation and its standing in the international community. Joining the Hague Convention demonstrates Nigeria's commitment to aligning its legal framework with international standards. This can showcase the country's willingness to participate in global efforts to address important legal matters, fostering a positive perception of Nigeria as a responsible and cooperative member of the international community. The Hague Convention provides standardized procedures for various cross-border legal matters, implementing these procedures can lead to more efficient and transparent legal processes. This can be particularly beneficial for cases involving child custody, international adoption, and the enforcement of judgments, reducing delays and uncertainties in legal proceedings. Hence, becoming a signatory to the Hague Convention can lead to improved diplomatic relations with other signatory countries. This can strengthen bilateral and multilateral relationships, potentially leading to increased trade, cultural exchanges, and collaboration on various global issues (Nwocha, 2019).

The standardized procedures provided by the Hague Convention can offer greater legal certainty for individuals and businesses engaged in cross-border activities involving Nigeria. This can encourage foreign investment, trade, and tourism, as investors and tourists are more likely to engage with countries that have clear and well-defined legal processes. This convention will also focus on protecting the rights and interests of individuals, especially in cases involving children. By joining the Convention, Nigeria would signal its commitment to safeguarding the rights of its citizens and those of other signatory countries, which can lead to increased trust and respect internationally. This process can lead to legal reforms and improvements within the country's legal system and contribute to better governance, transparency, and adherence to human rights principles (Nwachukwu et al, 2020).

As a signatory, Nigeria would be part of an international network of countries that share best practices, information, and resources related to inter-country adoption. This cooperation can help improve adoption practices and provide better outcomes for children. This also requires countries to establish centralized adoption authorities and ensure that inter-country adoptions are carried out in a transparent and accountable manner. This can help prevent corruption, ensure ethical adoptions, and build trust in the adoption process (Chikwe, Obiageli & Okoye, 2022). Furthermore, becoming a signatory would provide legal certainty for all parties involved in inter-country adoptions. This includes adoptive parents, birth parents, and the adopted child.

Clear legal procedures and standards would streamline the adoption process and reduce potential complications (Penarrubia, Palacios & Roman, 2020). During an interview, a stakeholder stated that the number of potential adoptive families for Nigerian children will increase as well as families from Convention member countries would be more likely to consider adopting from Nigeria due to standardized processes and protections. This will enhance Nigerian's reputation and encourage positive relationships with other countries in matters related to adoption.

Overall, the Hague Convention will strengthen the processes of adoption and also make Nigeria more visible on the international adoption arena. This research will inform the public about the significance of child adoption as a tool for social welfare and national development if the government agrees to implement the Hague convention. This study also calls for developing proper adoption guidelines and procedures to ensure that child births in health facilities are registered, well documented and updated digitally regularly. In many parts of Nigeria, a lot of children are delivered by unsupervised and unregistered traditional birth attendants who make birth registrations difficult.

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